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Legislative Councils And Good Governance At The Local Government Level: Evidence From Delta State, 2014–2024

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the role of legislative councils in promoting good governance and accountability at the local government level in Delta State, Nigeria, between 2014 and 2024. Anchored on Social Contract Theory, the study conceptualized local governance as a reciprocal relationship between the government and the governed, where legislative oversight and representation constitute essential mechanisms for ensuring transparency, accountability, and responsiveness. The research adopted a mixed-method design, combining quantitative survey data from 350 respondents (comprising legislative officers and administrative staff) with qualitative interviews involving selected councillors, civil society actors, and community stakeholders. Statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation were used to analyze quantitative data, while thematic analysis guided the interpretation of interview findings. Results revealed that while legislative councils in Delta State perform crucial oversight and accountability functions, their effectiveness is undermined by state interference, inadequate funding, political patronage, and limited institutional capacity. The paper found that in other climes where legislative autonomy, transparency practices, and citizen engagement were stronger, governance outcomes improved significantly. The findings underscore the need to strengthen legislative independence, institutionalize capacity building, and promote civic participation to enhance the accountability framework at the grassroots. The paper concludes that reinforcing the social contract through effective local legislative governance is vital for deepening democracy and achieving sustainable local development, and recommended amongst others that Delta state government should strengthen Legislative autonomy and financial independence, as well as institutionalizing capacity building and legislative professionalization

Keywords: Accountability, Delta State, good governance, legislative councils, local government, oversight function, Social Contract Theory.

INTRODUCTION

Delta State, part of Nigeria's Niger-Delta region, has continued to enjoy substantial inflows from federal allocations and internally generated revenue. In 2024, for example, the state's internally generated revenue (IGR) rose sharply from about ₦83 billion in 2023 to roughly ₦157.8 billion in 2024, surpassing the earlier target of ₦110.3 billion (Nairametrics, 2025). Despite this demonstration of fiscal capacity, many communities at the grassroots have yet to witness meaningful improvements in environmental infrastructure, basic services, or quality of life. Abandoned or poorly executed local projects remain widespread, and citizens' expectations of local development are largely unmet. The paradox is stark: rising revenue but persistently weak outcomes at the local level.

A major contributor to this problem is weak accountability. Local government legislative councils whose functions include oversight of executive action, auditing expenditures, approving budgets, and ensuring service delivery are frequently compromised by corruption, weak enforcement, and collusion with local executives. Civil society actors, such as the New Delta Coalition, have repeatedly flagged under-reporting of revenue, alleged fraud in revenue collection, and the heavy reliance on external (federal/state) transfers rather than sustainable internal revenue (Nairametrics, 2025). Such allegations raise serious concerns about the capacity and willingness of legislative councils to enforce accountability, curb abuse, and ensure that revenues serve public interest rather than private gain.

Although there have been government reforms and public commitments to transparency, the institutional and structural impediments remain strong. The *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* (1999, as amended) grants state governors considerable power over the finances of local governments, which undermines local autonomy and the ability of legislative councils to act independently. Meanwhile, capacity challenges such as a lack of staff skilled in procurement, audit, finance, monitoring, and evaluation persist in many councils. In the case of Delta State, although the Delta State Internal Revenue Service reported a revenue collection exceeding the 2024 target by approximately 143%, this achievement has not translated into proportional improvements in local service delivery, especially in environmental infrastructure, healthcare, education, or rural roads (The Blade NG, 2025).

Public perception and oversight indices further underscore the problem. In the *2024 Governance Accountability and Transparency Index* (G.A.T.I.), Delta State was ranked among the top ten Nigerian states for transparency and accountability (Delta State Government, 2024). Yet many citizens continue to complain that local governments fail to provide basic amenities, that legislative oversight is weak, and that councillors rarely challenge executive excesses in practice. Complaints range from abandoned projects to disbursed funds without visible purchases. The discrepancy between state-level praise for transparency and the actual conduct of local authorities suggests that symbolic recognition does not always amount to operational accountability.

Moreover, internal revenue growth has encountered its own limitations. While the absolute revenue figures improved, civil society groups have noted that the share of IGR in the state budget has shown a downward trend: moving from about 17.35% in 2023 to around 16.35% in 2024, with projections for 2025 hovering near 15% (Vanguard News, 2024). This dynamic indicates that despite rising collections, Delta State remains heavily dependent on federal allocations, limiting the fiscal space in which legislative councils might assert stronger oversight.

These conditions reflect a “gap” between formal institutional reforms and actual governance practices. Although the state has enacted legislative frameworks such as audit forums, criminal justice reforms, budget transparency policies, and revenue performance improvements, but the local government legislative councils often remain weak in practice or even complicit in poor governance. For instance, despite state government pronouncements on oversight and fiscal discipline, critics argue that oversight bodies remain under-resourced and lack the autonomy to enforce sanctions on errant executives (Vanguard News, 2024). The persistence of state interference, political patronage, tenure insecurity for local officials, and dominance of political godfathers in local politics further erode effective accountability.

Egobueze (2020) argues that legislative bodies are intended to be watchdogs over public funds and executive excess, but in many Nigerian contexts they have become “docile” or co-opted to the corruption deficit, serving as “hunting dogs” rather than genuine oversight institutions. His studies in Rivers State highlight how weak institutional design, dominance of the executive corruption, and lack of independence limit legislative councils’ capacity to enforce accountability. Moreover, Egobueze and Dumnu (2020) emphasize that the mere existence of oversight powers is insufficient, what matters is the political will, structural insulation, and institutional support that enable those powers to be exercised meaningfully. In local government contexts, these constraints manifest in rubber-stamping of budgets, collusive approval of overdrafts, or failure to disallow irregular expenditures.

The consequences of this accountability vacuum are severe for Delta State citizens. Poor environmental management, dilapidated infrastructure (roads, water, electricity), degraded health and education facilities, and neglect of rural areas are recurring complaints. Many communities, particularly in flood-prone or erosion-vulnerable locales, remain exposed to environmental shocks

with inadequate state support. The inability of local legislative councils to enforce oversight contributes directly to the persistence of these deficits.

In summary, although Delta State has made some noteworthy strides in revenue mobilization and has earned visibility in accountability indices, the fundamental problems of disconnect between revenue and service delivery, weak legislative oversight, structural interference, under-resourced councils, and public distrust endure. This study therefore aims to examine how effective local government legislative councils in Delta State have been in ensuring accountability between 2014 and 2024; to identify the principal legal, institutional, and political bottlenecks; and to assess how reforms and revenue gains translate (or fail to) into better outcomes at the grassroots level. The main objective of this study is to assess the effectiveness of local government legislative councils in exercising oversight and promoting accountability in Delta State between 2014 to 2024.

SOCIAL CONTRACT THEORY AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN GOVERNANCE

This paper is grounded in social contract theory, a classical framework that links the legitimacy of political authority to the consent and expectations of the governed. The theory offers a normative perspective through which to assess the duties of rulers and the rights of citizens in democratic governance, particularly regarding accountability and oversight.

Thomas Hobbes is often credited with crystallizing the modern form of social contract theory. Hobbes, born in 1588, presented the idea that in the absence of a strong central authority, life would be “solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short” (Mukki, 2008). To escape this chaos, individuals hypothetically surrendered some of their freedoms to a sovereign power that would guarantee order and security (Lain, 2007; Mukki, 2008). Later thinkers such as John Locke (1632–1704) and Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712–1778) refined and reinterpreted Hobbes’s ideas, emphasizing consent, natural rights, and the general will (Chubah, Nweke, & Emesiani, 2019; Ibrahim & Nurudeen, 2022). In more recent discourse, Nweke (2021) defines the social compact as an agreement delineating the duties and rights of the ruled and rulers. The core assumption is that people exit a state of nature characterized by uncertainty and insecurity and establish government to protect life, property, and public welfare. Rousseau’s notion of the “general will” asserts that true sovereignty lies in the collective interests of citizens (Okeke, 2019). Thus, state legitimacy is contingent on adherence to that contract: when leaders breach it, they lose moral authority and must be held to account (Shaapera, 2014).

Social contract theory is not without challengers. Critics argue that the idea of a pre-political “golden age” is historically unfounded, that contractual consent in such a state is hypothetical and not real, and that such contracts cannot bind future generations (Nweke, 2022). Some contend that citizenship is a legal obligation, not a voluntary contract; others view such theoretical agreements as mere abstractions (Asogwa & Nnamchi, 2020). Nonetheless, the theory remains deeply relevant to democratic governance because it frames the relationship between citizens and rulers as essentially fiduciary or agency-based.

In democratic settings, social contract theory underscores the agency relationship between the people (principals) and their representatives (agents). The populace grants powers to officials to govern in their interests, and those officials are morally and politically bound to act with fidelity, transparency, and accountability (Appadorai, 1975; Egugbo, 2022). Egugbo (2022) argues that public accountability is the binding social contract, it demands that officeholders make periodic disclosures of public transactions, be answerable for decisions, and offer redress for failure. In effect, the contract gives rise to institutional structures (legislatures, courts, audit agencies) that mediate citizens’ demands and enforce compliance. Hence, when public officials abuse power, mismanage resources, or fail to deliver, they violate their implicit or explicit covenant with citizens. In such cases, the people are justified in using electoral, judicial, or social means to withdraw consent or demand accountability. The degree to which a polity fulfills this contract is a measure of good governance: a system that tolerates impunity, corruption, or executive overreach undermines its normative foundation.

While social contract theory provides the normative justification, operational mechanisms are needed to enforce accountability. Here, legislative oversight plays a central role (Egobueze, 2016). The legislature is the institutional embodiment of the people’s will, endowed with powers to scrutinize, monitor, and sanction executive misconduct (Fatile, 2023). In Nigeria, oversight functions are constitutionally mandated to check executive excess, promote transparency, and ensure that laws and

budgets are executed faithfully (Fatile, 2023; Oversight Functions of the Legislature, n.d.). However, oversight is often compromised by weak institutional capacity, executive interference, lack of autonomy, and resource constraints (Nwaegbu, 2022; Oversight Functions of the Legislature, n.d.).

In his work, Egobueze (2015) highlights the challenges of accountability and financial discipline in the legislature. He notes that public demand has grown for accountability at all levels, but that actual legislative practice often falls short due to inadequate enforcement, political pressure, and weak institutional culture. Egobueze's scholarship emphasizes that oversight bodies must be insulated, empowered, and resourced; otherwise, they become "hunting dogs" rather than watchdogs (a metaphor echoed in Fatile, 2023).

STUDY AREA

Delta State is one of the 36 states of Nigeria, located in the South-South geopolitical zone. It was created on August 27, 1991, following the division of the former Bendel State into Edo and Delta States. Historically, before its creation, the territory that now constitutes Delta State was part of the Western Region (1951–1963), later the Midwestern Region (1963–1976), and then Bendel State (1976–1991) (Delta State Government, n.d.-a). The capital of Delta State is Asaba, situated on the western bank of the River Niger, serving as the administrative and political hub of the state (Community Engagement South-South Presidency, n.d.).

Geographically, Delta State lies approximately between longitude 5°00'E and 6°45'E and latitude 5°00'N and 6°30'N. It occupies a total landmass of about 17,100 square kilometres, with a coastline stretching about 160 to 163 kilometres along the Atlantic Ocean (Delta State Government, n.d.-a). The topography varies significantly, ranging from the swampy, riverine terrain of the south to the drier upland areas in the north. The state shares boundaries with Edo State to the north, Anambra and Rivers States to the east, Bayelsa State to the south, and Ondo State to the northwest. Its southern boundary opens into the Bight of Benin along the Atlantic coast (Delta State Government, n.d.-a).

According to projections by the Delta State Bureau of Statistics, the state's population was estimated at 5.6 million people as of 2022 (Delta State Government, n.d.-b). Administratively, Delta State is divided into 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs)—Aniocha North, Aniocha South, Bomadi, Burutu, Ethiope East, Ethiope West, Ika North East, Ika South, Isoko North, Isoko South, Ndokwa East, Ndokwa West, Okpe, Oshimili North, Oshimili South, Patani, Sapele, Udu, Ughelli North, Ughelli South, Ukwuani, Uvwie, Warri North, Warri South, and Warri South West (BlackGeeks Nigeria, 2024). Each LGA is administered by a local government chairman and legislative council, which form the executive and legislative arms at the grassroots level.

Delta State operates under Nigeria's federal system, comprising three branches of government, the legislative, executive, and judicial. The legislative arm, represented by the Delta State House of Assembly, consists of 30 elected members responsible for law-making and oversight functions. The executive arm is led by the Governor and Deputy Governor, supported by commissioners and special advisers overseeing various ministries and parastatals. The judiciary, headed by the Chief Judge of the State, includes the High Court, Magistrate Courts, and Customary Courts (Delta State iHub, n.d.).

At the local government level, each council mirrors this structure: a legislative council composed of councillors, a leader, and principal officers. These councils are responsible for enacting by-laws, supervising local projects, and ensuring grassroots accountability. There is also an executive arm led by the chairman and his deputy, supervisors and the bureaucracy. They execute the Bye - laws made by the Councils, and implement such other policies that shape governance.

Delta State is renowned for its multi-ethnic and multicultural diversity, with five major ethnic groups: Urhobo, Ijaw, Isoko, Itsekiri, and Igbo (Anioma people). The people share deep-rooted cultural traditions expressed through festivals, arts, music, and religion. While Christianity is the dominant faith, Islam and indigenous belief systems are also practiced. The cultural diversity enriches social interactions but can also complicate local governance when ethnic considerations influence political representation and resource allocation (Delta State Government, n.d.-b).

Economically, Delta State is a vital contributor to Nigeria's GDP, primarily through oil and gas production, as it forms part of the Niger Delta region. The state also engages in agriculture, producing crops such as cassava, yam, oil palm, rice, and rubber. Other key economic activities include fishing, trade, and services. However, environmental degradation resulting from oil exploration, particularly in communities such as Warri, Burutu, and Bomadi poses serious developmental challenges (Delta State

Government, n.d.-b). The combination of swampy terrain and inadequate infrastructure also constrains service delivery, transportation, and local economic expansion.

The combination of Delta State’s geography, ethnic diversity, and administrative complexity presents both opportunities and challenges for governance and accountability. The dispersed nature of its 25 LGAs many located in difficult-to-reach coastal or riverine areas hampers efficient monitoring, project implementation, and oversight. Furthermore, the political structure often concentrates fiscal power at the state level, limiting the autonomy of local government legislative councils. Consequently, this setting is ideal for examining the dynamics between local governance, legislative oversight, and accountability mechanisms.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Presentation of Data

This part presents and analyzes data obtained from the questionnaire administered on the topic “Legislative Councils and Good Governance at the Local Government Level: Evidence from Delta State, 2014–2024” The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages to ensure clarity and ease of interpretation.

Table 1: Response Rate of Administered Questionnaires

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	386	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	36	9
Number of questionnaires retrieved	350	91
Total	386	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

The data in Table 1 show that out of the 386 questionnaires administered, 36 (representing 9%) were not returned, while 350 (representing 91%) were duly completed and retrieved. This implies that the overall response rate was **91%**, which is considered excellent and adequate for reliable data analysis.

Table 2: Breakdown of Returned/Valid Questionnaires by Respondent Category

Respondent Category	Questionnaires Distributed	Questionnaires Returned	Percentage of Returned (%)
Legislative Officers	270	250	65
Administrative Staff	116	100	26
Total	386	350	91

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

Table 2 presents the distribution of questionnaires across respondent categories. Out of 270 questionnaires distributed to legislative officers, 250 were returned, representing 65% of the total. Similarly, 116 questionnaires were given to administrative staff, out of which 100 were returned, representing 26%. This yielded a total of 350 valid responses (91%), indicating a robust and representative response rate for the study.

Table 3: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender Frequency (f) Percentage (%)

Male	200	57
Female	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

As shown in Table 3, 200 respondents (57%) were male, while 150 respondents (43%) were female. This indicates that the study population was male-dominated. However, both genders were adequately represented, ensuring that the responses reflect balanced perspectives. The gender composition did not significantly influence the overall outcome of the research.

Table 4: Educational Qualifications of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
FSLC	50	14
SSCE	90	26
HND/BSc/PGD	110	31
MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD	100	29
Total	350	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

Table 4 illustrates the educational background of respondents. The data reveal that 50 respondents (14%) possessed the First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC), 90 respondents (26%) held the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE), 110 respondents (31%) obtained either a Higher National Diploma (HND), Bachelor of Science (BSc), or Postgraduate Diploma (PGD), while 100 respondents (29%) had postgraduate qualifications such as MSc, MPA, MBA, or PhD. This distribution indicates that a large proportion of respondents were well-educated and had sufficient knowledge and understanding of local government legislative processes and accountability mechanisms in Delta State.

Table 5: Length of Service of Respondents in the Council

Years of Service	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
01–09 years	40	11
10–20 years	100	29
21–30 years	200	57
31 years and above	10	3
Total	350	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

As shown in Table 5, 40 respondents (11%) had served between 1 and 9 years, while 100 respondents (29%) had been in service between 10 and 20 years. A larger proportion—200 respondents (57%)—had served between 21 and 30 years, and only 10 respondents (3%) had served for more than 31 years. This finding indicates that the majority of the respondents had considerable experience in the local government system. Consequently, their opinions and responses are deemed credible and relevant to the study, as they are well-informed about the internal workings of local government legislative councils and issues of accountability.

The demographic and response data presented in this section demonstrate that the study achieved a high response rate with a well-balanced representation across gender, education, and years of service. The respondents' experience and educational background provide a strong foundation for credible insights into how legislative councils influence accountability and governance in Delta State's local government system.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question: *How effective are the local government legislative councils in exercising oversight and promoting accountability in Delta State?*

Table 6. Mean and Standard Deviation on the Effectiveness of Local Government Legislative Councils in Exercising Oversight and Promoting Accountability in Governance in Delta State

S/N ITEMS	Legislative Officers (N=675)	Decision	Administrative Staff (N=335)	Decision
1	State interference in local government legislative functions limits the exercise of oversight in local government accountability and governance. $\bar{X} = 2.70, SD = 1.44$	Agree	$\bar{X} = 2.55, SD = 2.55$	Agree
2	Legislative oversight does not engender accountability in governance. $\bar{X} = 3.66, SD = 0.68$	Agree	$\bar{X} = 3.35, SD = 0.75$	Agree
3	Inadequate knowledge of local government legislative officers hinders legislative functions in oversight and ensuring accountability. $\bar{X} = 3.30, SD = 0.89$	Agree	$\bar{X} = 3.35, SD = 0.75$	Agree
4	Political godfathers direct the extent of legislative performance and thus hinder fiscal accountability in governance. $\bar{X} = 3.50, SD = 0.64$	Agree	$\bar{X} = 3.40$	Agree
5	Local government legislative councils are ineffective since the outcomes of their investigations are often politically motivated. $\bar{X} = 3.38, SD = 0.85$	Agree	$\bar{X} = 3.20, SD = 0.87$	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2024. Benchmark = 2.50

The data presented in Table 6 assess the perceived effectiveness of local government legislative councils in exercising oversight and promoting accountability in Delta State. The analysis is based on responses from both **legislative officers** and **administrative staff**, with a decision benchmark of 2.50. For **Item 1**, which assessed whether *state interference in local government legislative functions limits the exercise of oversight in governance*, legislative officers recorded a mean of **2.70**, while administrative staff recorded **2.55**. Both mean scores are above the 2.50 benchmark, indicating consensus that excessive state interference constrains the independence and effectiveness of local legislative councils in performing oversight roles. This finding aligns with earlier arguments that state governments' control over local affairs weakens local autonomy and transparency (Akindele & Olaopa, 2020).

For **Item 2**, which examined whether *legislative oversight engenders accountability in governance*, legislative officers had a mean of **3.66** while administrative staff reported **3.35**, both exceeding the benchmark. Respondents agreed that legislative oversight has not been sufficiently effective in ensuring accountability. This outcome suggests that despite existing institutional frameworks, oversight activities are often superficial or politically influenced rather than grounded in performance monitoring (Oviasuyi, Idada, & Isiraojie, 2010).

Item 3 focused on whether *inadequate knowledge among legislative officers hinders effective oversight*. The mean scores were **3.30** for legislative officers and **3.35** for administrative staff, both indicating agreement. Respondents recognized that many councillors lack adequate training in legislative procedures, budgeting, and audit mechanisms, which limits their capacity to enforce accountability effectively. This finding supports Ezeani (2012), who emphasized the importance of capacity building for local government legislators to enhance governance outcomes.

Item 4 assessed the claim that *political godfathers influence legislative performance and hinder fiscal accountability*. Legislative officers recorded a mean of **3.50**, while administrative staff recorded **3.40**, again above the benchmark. The result demonstrates a strong perception that political interference significantly shapes legislative conduct and weakens the independence of councillors. According to

Agagu (2008), such patron-client relationships erode democratic accountability at the grassroots level and promote selective enforcement of laws and oversight responsibilities.

Item 5 examined whether *local government legislative councils are ineffective because their investigations are politically motivated*. Legislative officers had a mean of **3.38**, and administrative staff scored **3.20**. Both groups agreed that political bias and external influence undermine the objectivity of council investigations. This suggests that oversight reports and committee findings are often influenced by partisan or personal interests, reducing their credibility and impact on governance outcomes.

From the overall analysis, all items recorded mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50 for both respondent categories. This indicates a general consensus that local government legislative councils in Delta State face significant institutional, political, and capacity-related constraints in exercising oversight and promoting accountability.

While respondents acknowledged that legislative councils perform oversight roles, their effectiveness is limited by state interference, political influence, inadequate capacity, and low institutional autonomy. Nevertheless, the aggregate results also suggest that these councils remain functionally active, albeit with reduced independence and effectiveness.

Thus, the findings imply that although the local government legislative councils contribute to promoting accountability in governance, their impact is moderate and constrained by systemic challenges. Effective oversight would require greater administrative independence, professional training, and insulation from partisan control.

In response to the research question, which says: “*How effective are the local government legislative councils in exercising oversight and promoting accountability in Delta State?*” the study concludes that both legislative and administrative respondents perceive the councils as partially effective. Their roles are hampered by political interference, inadequate knowledge, and weak institutional capacity.

To enhance effectiveness, there is a need for greater legislative autonomy, capacity development programs for councillors, and reform of oversight mechanisms to ensure transparency and reduce external influence in local governance processes.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Effectiveness of Local Government Legislative Councils in Exercising Oversight and Promoting Accountability in Delta State

This section examines the effectiveness of local government legislative councils in exercising oversight and promoting accountability in governance in Delta State. The analysis combines quantitative data from survey responses with qualitative evidence obtained from interviews, alongside insights from existing scholarly and institutional literature. The overall objective is to assess the extent to which legislative councils contribute to transparent and accountable governance and to identify the challenges that hinder their full effectiveness.

The results from the quantitative survey reveal that the majority of respondents, including both legislative officers and administrative staff, perceive that the legislative councils’ effectiveness is limited by several institutional and political constraints. Regarding state interference in local government legislative functions, legislative officers reported a mean score of 2.70 with a standard deviation of 1.44, while administrative staff recorded a mean of 2.55. Both values are above the benchmark of 2.50, indicating that respondents agree that interference from the state government limits the councils’ ability to exercise independent oversight. This reflects the broader constitutional framework of Nigeria, where the 1999 Constitution grants state governors significant control over local government finances, thereby weakening legislative autonomy (Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, as amended).

For the item assessing whether legislative oversight engenders accountability in governance, legislative officers recorded a mean of 3.66 (SD = 0.68), while administrative staff recorded 3.35 (SD = 0.75). These results suggest that oversight efforts are perceived as inadequate in fostering genuine accountability. The problem is not necessarily the absence of oversight activities, but their ineffectiveness due to lack of enforcement power, insufficient follow-up, and political interference. Similar findings were reported by Yusuf and Ojoduwa (2022), who observed that in Nigeria’s Fourth

Republic, oversight processes often fail to translate into measurable accountability outcomes due to executive dominance and weak institutional capacity.

A related problem is the inadequate technical knowledge and capacity of local government legislators. The survey result for this item yielded mean scores of 3.30 among legislative officers and 3.35 among administrative staff, both of which are above the benchmark. Respondents agreed that insufficient knowledge of financial management, auditing, procurement, and budget analysis among councillors hinders effective oversight. This corroborates the findings of Fatile and Adejuwon (2023), who noted that legislative oversight in Nigeria is constitutionally guaranteed but undermined by limited technical competence and poor training of legislators. In Delta State, many councillors enter office without prior experience in public finance or legislative procedures, leading to dependence on administrative officers or the executive arm for guidance, which undermines independent scrutiny.

Political interference, especially from godfathers and party elites, is another major obstacle. The mean responses for this item were 3.50 for legislative officers and 3.40 for administrative staff, showing strong agreement that political patrons influence legislative performance and thereby obstruct fiscal accountability. The dominance of political godfathers constrains councillors' freedom to question executive excesses or expose corruption. As Nwaegbu (2022) explained, the culture of political patronage and loyalty to power brokers weakens legislative independence and reduces the legislature's oversight role to a mere formality. In practice, councillors often fear political repercussions if they challenge decisions that conflict with party or state interests.

The final quantitative item assessed whether the local government legislative councils are ineffective because their investigative outcomes are politically motivated. Legislative officers gave a mean of 3.38 (SD = 0.85), and administrative staff 3.20 (SD = 0.87). These results imply that many respondents believe oversight investigations often serve political rather than developmental or accountability purposes. This view aligns with research by Abdulfattah, Saheed, and Shittu-Adenuga (2022), who found that legislative oversight in Nigeria often lacks neutrality and is influenced by political alignments, undermining the principle of checks and balances.

In summary, all five items in the quantitative analysis recorded mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50, showing that both legislative officers and administrative staff agree that, while oversight structures exist, their effectiveness in promoting accountability is compromised by structural, political, and capacity-related challenges.

Qualitative interviews conducted with legislative councillors, administrative officers, and civil society representatives further illuminate these findings. A councillor, T. Ododofor (personal communication, October 21, 2024), stated that public hearings are important for promoting accountability because they create awareness among citizens and compel responses from government officials. However, he emphasized that these hearings "only make the government accountable to some extent," since political interference and the concentration of financial control at the state level often dilute the councils' recommendations. Similarly, R. Bodsmi (personal communication, October 21, 2024) noted that although budget and finance committees are mandated to scrutinize local government budgets, they often lack adequate resources and expertise to detect financial mismanagement. J. Tebu, a civil society activist (personal communication, October 24, 2024), criticized the Public Complaints Commission, stating that it is legally established to handle citizens' complaints and monitor official abuse, but in Delta State it is "virtually non-functional." J. Obule (personal communication, October 24, 2024) added that while the councils possess procedural tools such as oral and written questions, committee hearings, and plenary interrogations, these are rarely used to hold executives accountable. According to him, "If committees were open to public scrutiny and had the power to summon senior officials, oversight would be more than symbolic."

These interviews show that the mechanisms for accountability exist in form but not always in function. Councils conduct oversight activities but often fail to enforce their findings. The limited impact is linked to a lack of follow-up and the political dependency of councillors on the state and party structure. Egobueze (2018) similarly observed that the effectiveness of local government legislative oversight in Nigeria depends on the level of autonomy and the enforcement power granted to local councils. Where these are weak, oversight becomes procedural rather than substantive.

The institutional and legal frameworks underpinning legislative oversight are robust in theory. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) mandates state Houses of Assembly and local councils to maintain transparency in budgeting and expenditure. Sections 120 and 125 empower them

to review government spending and ensure that funds are used for intended purposes. Likewise, the Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre (PLAC, 2016) underscores that oversight committees such as Public Accounts Committees are essential mechanisms for ensuring fiscal discipline. However, these mechanisms are effective only when supported by political will, financial autonomy, and technical capacity—all of which remain weak in many Nigerian states, including Delta.

In practice, the Delta State context reflects the national pattern of legislative weakness and executive dominance. According to Egobueze (2018), the legislative councils' oversight role is constrained by the lack of independence, politicization of proceedings, and weak administrative support systems. Nwaegbu (2022) also emphasizes that oversight institutions are often underfunded, poorly staffed, and unable to enforce sanctions when wrongdoing is detected. In the case of Delta State, these challenges are compounded by the close relationship between the local and state executives, as well as the absence of strong citizen engagement in legislative processes.

Despite these limitations, the local government legislative councils still play a symbolic role in promoting transparency. Their existence provides a framework for potential accountability and public participation. However, the study reveals that the councils' influence on actual governance outcomes remains minimal. Respondents frequently mentioned that while Delta State is ranked among the top Nigerian states for transparency in the 2024 Governance Accountability and Transparency Index, citizens still perceive local governments as failing to provide basic services or manage resources effectively (Delta State Government, 2024). This disparity suggests that official recognition of transparency does not necessarily translate into functional accountability at the grassroots level.

Comparatively, the challenges identified in Delta State mirror those documented across Nigeria. Yusuf and Ojoduwa (2022) observed that oversight contributes to democratic consolidation but remains inconsistent due to weak institutions and lack of enforcement mechanisms. Similarly, Fatile and Adejuwon (2023) emphasized that oversight in the Nigerian context requires not just legal provisions but institutional strengthening and sustained political commitment. The Policy and Legal Advocacy Centre (PLAC, 2016) further argued that oversight must be supported by adequate funding, legal authority, and citizen awareness to prevent it from becoming ceremonial. In this regard, Delta State's legislative councils reflect broader national trends of procedural oversight with limited tangible outcomes.

Based on the evidence from survey responses, interviews, and literature, several major factors explain the councils' limited effectiveness. First, state and executive interference remains the most prominent constraint. Governors often control the release of funds to local governments, limiting the fiscal independence required for effective legislative scrutiny. Second, many councillors lack technical knowledge in key areas such as financial analysis, procurement monitoring, and audit interpretation, which restricts their ability to detect irregularities. Third, the pervasive influence of political godfathers reduces independence and encourages self-censorship among councillors. Fourth, even when councils identify instances of maladministration, enforcement mechanisms are weak or non-existent, leading to inaction. Finally, accountability mechanisms such as the Public Complaints Commission and ombudsman offices remain inactive, reducing citizen participation and external checks.

To enhance accountability, several strategies are necessary. First, greater fiscal and administrative autonomy should be granted to local government councils to reduce state interference. Second, systematic capacity-building programs should be instituted to train councillors and administrative staff in budgeting, auditing, and legislative procedure. Third, oversight findings should carry legal sanctions for non-compliance, ensuring that executive officers can be held responsible for misuse of funds. Fourth, civil society engagement should be strengthened to provide external pressure and monitoring. Lastly, legislative reports and audit outcomes should be publicly disseminated to foster transparency and encourage citizen oversight.

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicate that while local government legislative councils in Delta State possess the institutional framework for oversight and accountability, their practical effectiveness remains limited. Both legislative officers and administrative staff agree that interference, inadequate capacity, political manipulation, and weak enforcement mechanisms constrain the councils' performance. Interviews further confirm that oversight mechanisms, though present, are underutilized or politically compromised. These findings are consistent with national and international studies on legislative oversight in Nigeria. Strengthening autonomy, building technical capacity, and

fostering civic participation are therefore essential steps toward transforming legislative councils from symbolic institutions into effective instruments of accountability and good governance.

CONCLUSION

The study on *Legislative Councils and Good Governance at the Local Government Level: Evidence from Delta State (2014–2024)* revealed that accountability and transparency in governance are closely tied to the effectiveness of local government legislative councils. The legislature remains indispensable to democratic governance, serving as the institutional mechanism that ensures checks and balances, transparency, and citizen representation as enshrined in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). When legislative oversight is weak or compromised, executive arbitrariness and administrative misconduct flourish, undermining the principles of good governance. Legislative councils play a central role in enforcing accountability through oversight, investigation, and public engagement. Effective oversight enables legislators to evaluate government performance, monitor policy implementation, and expose maladministration or corruption. However, findings indicate that state interference, political patronage, and limited institutional capacity continue to hinder legislative autonomy and effectiveness at the local level. Many councillors lack the technical skills and resources needed for effective scrutiny of executive actions, while political godfathers often dictate the limits of legislative independence.

Furthermore, financial dependence on the executive arm—especially the control of local government allocations and remuneration—undermines legislative objectivity and weakens institutional checks. Despite these constraints, certain reforms, such as the Delta State Local Government Law Amendment (2013) and the 2024 Power Sector Bill, show potential for strengthening participatory governance and legislative engagement.

To enhance good governance, legislative councils must be adequately funded, trained, and insulated from political interference. Committees should complete and act upon oversight recommendations, while legislators uphold ethical standards and self-accountability. Ultimately, sustainable governance in Delta State depends on empowering local legislative councils to operate transparently, independently, and in genuine service to the people they represent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Strengthen Legislative Autonomy and Financial Independence

To ensure effective oversight, local government legislative councils in Delta State must be institutionally and financially autonomous. The current constitutional arrangement that channels local government allocations through state governments (as stipulated in Section 162 of the 1999 Constitution) should be revisited. Legislative advocacy should push for constitutional amendments guaranteeing direct fiscal transfers from the Federation Account to local councils. This reform will reduce executive manipulation and foster independent budgetary oversight and transparency.

2. Institutionalize Capacity Building and Legislative Professionalization

Regular training and retraining programs for councillors and legislative staff are critical for enhancing the quality of lawmaking and oversight. Collaboration with the National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies (NILDS), universities, and development partners should be institutionalized to build competence in areas such as budgeting, procurement, auditing, and policy evaluation. Establishing a Legislative Research and Documentation Unit within each local council would further improve evidence-based decision-making.

3. Reform Oversight Mechanisms and Committee Systems

Committees should be granted statutory powers and operational independence to conduct inquiries without political interference. Standing committees on finance, works, health, and education should adopt performance-based oversight using measurable indicators of service delivery. Legislative oversight reports must be made public and followed by mandatory implementation tracking, ensuring that recommendations are acted upon. A digital monitoring dashboard could enhance transparency and citizen engagement in tracking oversight outcomes.

4. Enhance Public Participation and Civic Oversight

Good governance thrives on citizen inclusion. Legislative councils should adopt open government principles by holding regular town hall meetings, publishing budgets online, and inviting civil society organizations (CSOs) to legislative hearings. Establishing Community Accountability Forums (CAFs)

within wards can bridge the gap between the legislature and citizens, creating a participatory framework for local development priorities and ensuring that citizens hold their representatives accountable.

5. Reduce Political Patronage and Executive Domination

To curb the pervasive influence of state governors and political godfathers, there should be a strict enforcement of codes of conduct and conflict-of-interest laws for councillors. The State Independent Electoral Commission (SIEC) should be restructured to guarantee non-partisan local elections. Internal rules of procedure should also be reviewed to safeguard legislative independence and limit external interference in council deliberations.

6. Establish Performance Audits and Legislative Scorecards

Each council should institutionalize annual legislative performance audits, evaluating the number of motions, bills, and oversight reports completed. The publication of legislative scorecards—as pioneered by organizations such as BudGIT and OrderPaper Nigeria—can increase transparency and public confidence in local councils while motivating councillors to perform effectively.

7. Promote Collaboration and Policy Synergy

Finally, effective governance requires collaboration among the legislative, executive, and civil society sectors. Intergovernmental policy platforms should be developed where state and local legislative bodies share best practices, harmonize laws, and align development strategies. Encouraging such synergy will enhance coordination, resource optimization, and accountability across governance levels.

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